

Cosm: Collective Switched Motion for Fast and Accurate Sparse Ising Optimization

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Abstract—We introduce **Collective Switched Motion (Cosm)**, a dynamical system-based heuristic algorithm. Cosm combines locally interacting continuous circular variables with novel global coordination rules that facilitate collective dynamics. Pairwise interactions occur sequentially over a set of conflict-free edge partitions, resulting in an interaction network that switches periodically. Unlike conventional gradient-based approaches, Cosm employs structured, non-smooth switching dynamics with finite-magnitude interactions that sustain collective fluctuations and promote exploration beyond local minima. A correlated perturbation mechanism further promotes coordinated cluster motion in the circular phase space. On the three largest Ising problems from the Gset suite, which have 10,000–20,000 variables and represent 2D spin glasses, Cosm attains the optimal solutions (verified with an exact solver) heuristically for the first time. On two large bounded-degree non-lattice graph instances, Cosm reduces the state-of-the-art times-to-target from hundreds of hours to 36–303 s. Results on benchmark problems with tuned hardness suggest favorable scaling relative to previously characterized dynamical solvers. These results suggest that Cosm’s synthesis of local interactions, structured switching dynamics, and global coordination provides an effective computational framework for sparse optimization.

Index Terms—Binary optimization, collective computation, combinatorial optimization, dynamical system, heuristic algorithm, Ising, Max-Cut, QUBO, switched network, time-varying network.

I. INTRODUCTION

AN important class of optimization problems involves binary variables coupled through highly sparse pairwise interactions. These sparse Ising-type problems (including Max-Cut and quadratic unconstrained binary optimization/QUBO formulations) have widespread applications such as task scheduling, low-density parity-check (LDPC) decoding, spin glass simulations, and power systems optimization [1] [2] [3]. Sparse local interaction structures are commonplace due to physical, communication, or architectural constraints. These problems often give rise to rugged landscapes and frustration that challenge exact [4] [5] and approximate solvers such as semidefinite programming [6].

Sparse Ising-type problems are frequently addressed with physics-inspired heuristic algorithms such as simulated annealing and parallel tempering [7]. Newer dynamical system-based heuristics have gained attention, particularly the Simulated Bifurcation Machine (SBM) introduced by Goto et al. [8], which has demonstrated state-of-the-art performance on dense

problem instances [9] [10]. Although SBM and several other dynamical approaches, such as the Coherent Ising Machine (CIM), show promising characteristics, they find sparse optimization very challenging, as seen in a recent comparative study by Hou et al. [11]. Many existing approaches rely on smooth relaxation, stochastic local exploration, or synchronization dynamics, each of which can prematurely freeze into metastable states.

A complementary direction that has gained traction in recent years explores the use of quantum mechanical resources—such as superposition, tunneling, and entanglement—to accelerate combinatorial optimization. Two prominent approaches are quantum annealing [12] [13] [14] [15] and the Quantum Approximate Optimization Algorithm (QAOA) [16] [17]. Despite their conceptual appeal, it should be noted that there is currently no clear evidence that quantum algorithms for combinatorial optimization provide exponential speedups for real-world NP-hard problems, nor compelling evidence that they yield consistent practical advantages in heuristic settings. Moreover, many sparse optimization problems involve graphs with arbitrary connectivity and tens of thousands of variables, posing a significant engineering challenge for quantum processors.

Further motivation for new approaches comes from the field of Ising spin glasses, which are disordered and frustrated magnetic systems with highly rugged energy landscapes. Simulation of spin glasses has close connections to combinatorial optimization; many hard problems can be formulated as Ising models with disorder, frustration, and ruggedness. 2D spin glasses have been one of the canonical benchmark problems for optimizing solvers [18]. Parisi’s discoveries of patterns in disordered materials [19] led to a better understanding of these rugged energy landscapes and gave rise to the influential parallel tempering algorithm. However, upon surveying the field in 2025, Parisi and authors Dahlberg et al. report that, beyond parallel tempering, algorithmic progress in this domain has been largely stagnant over the past two decades and that new algorithms are needed for both physics and engineering applications [20].

Taken together, these observations highlight a critical gap: while both classical and emerging quantum approaches have made progress, there remains a need for new algorithmic approaches that can effectively address large-scale, sparse Ising-type optimization problems. In this work, we present a novel heuristic approach for such problems, called **Collective Switched Motion (Cosm)**. The main contributions of this paper are summarized as follows:

- We propose a switched dynamical system approach called sequential conflict-free search using edge-colored updates

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enabling efficient exploration of high-dimensional circular (phase) variable spaces.

- We provide a dynamical interpretation of Cosm as a periodically switched system with non-smooth finite-magnitude interactions, offering intuition for how persistent structured fluctuations may facilitate exploration of sparse energy landscapes.
- We introduce a novel correlated perturbation mechanism termed dual window twist that enhances cluster mobility along the unit circle and significantly improves solution quality.
- We present experimental results demonstrating substantial gains over existing approaches on three types of sparse, bounded-degree Ising benchmark problems.

II. COLLECTIVE SWITCHED MOTION – COSM

In this section, we cover the basics of Cosm, present the full pseudocode, and describe in detail two defining features.

A. Baseline Algorithmic Components

The Ising Hamiltonian is given by

$$H(\mathbf{s}) = - \sum_{(i,j) \in E_G} J_{ij} s_i s_j - \sum_i h_i s_i \quad (1)$$

with spin variables $s_i \in \{-1, +1\}$, edges (i,j) in the set E_G , pairwise interaction weights J_{ij} , and local bias fields h_i . In defining Cosm, we first relax the binary constraint on the variables and instead define variables x_i that live on a unit circle (i.e., a 1-sphere S^1), where $x_i \in [0, 360)$ degrees with $0 \sim 360$ (wrapped interval). Updates use modular arithmetic on $[0, 360)$. Circular variables have been employed in approaches such as oscillator Ising machines [21] [22] [23], XY machines [24], and semidefinite programming. Next, we replace the quadratic $s_i s_j$ term with a relaxed coupling term $v(x_i, x_j)$ that is a function of the minimum angular difference between the two variables. Specifically, we define the piecewise linear function

$$v(x_i, x_j) = 1 - \frac{|((x_i - x_j + 180) \bmod 360) - 180|}{90} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 1. Energy Functions for Ferromagnetic (FM) and Anti-Ferromagnetic (AFM) Couplings in Cosm. The quantity $x_i - x_j$ represents the minimum angular difference between two coupled circular variables.

where mod returns a nonnegative remainder and $v(\cdot)$ takes values in the continuous range $[-1, 1]$. This creates a coupling energy potential

$$f_{\text{pair}}(x_i, x_j) = -J_{ij}v(x_i, x_j) \quad (3)$$

that is v-shaped for ferromagnetic couplings and inverted-v-shaped for anti-ferromagnetic couplings, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The coupling energy is minimized when a ferromagnetically coupled (anti-ferromagnetically coupled) pair is at the same (diametrically opposite) position along the unit circle.

We then define the effect of a pairwise interaction on the two coupled variables. Fields are applied to each variable in the opposite direction of the partial derivatives of the coupling function. While $f_{\text{pair}}(\cdot)$ is not differentiable at 0 or ± 180 , we define a biased signum (sgn) function

$$\text{sgn}_b(x_i - x_j) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{for } x_i - x_j \geq 0 \\ -1 & \text{for } x_i - x_j < 0. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

and a selected generalized gradient

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial f_{\text{pair}}}{\partial x_i} &= -J_{ij}(-\text{sgn}_b(x_i - x_j)) \\ \frac{\partial f_{\text{pair}}}{\partial x_j} &= -J_{ij}(\text{sgn}_b(x_i - x_j)). \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

With the inclusion of a time-dependent step size α_t , the resulting contributions from a pairwise interaction are defined to be

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta x_i &= -\alpha_t \frac{\partial f_{\text{pair}}}{\partial x_i} = -\alpha_t J_{ij} \text{sgn}_b(x_i - x_j) \\ \Delta x_j &= -\alpha_t \frac{\partial f_{\text{pair}}}{\partial x_j} = \alpha_t J_{ij} \text{sgn}_b(x_i - x_j). \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

Note that unlike sinusoidal interactions, the interactions here maintain finite update magnitudes independent of angular separation and do not weaken continuously with angular distance. Given the symmetry of (4) and (6), there are just two possible outcomes, analogous to bang-bang-like control policies which have two extremal control actions. Interactions of this type have been used in recent works such as Refs. [23] [25] [26].

The entire relaxed objective function in Cosm is

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = - \sum_{(i,j) \in E_G} J_{ij}v(x_i, x_j) = \sum_{(i,j) \in E_G} f_{\text{pair}}(x_i, x_j) \quad (7)$$

with local bias fields omitted for clarity.

In this context, a traditional gradient descent approach would employ an update rule of the form

$$\mathbf{x}_{t+1} = \mathbf{x}_t - \alpha_t \nabla f(\mathbf{x}_t) \quad (8)$$

where ∇f is the selected generalized gradient. We find that with circular variables and the model described above, standard gradient descent does not provide competitive accuracy on the sparse problems we test. Absent a formal proof, we provide an intuition for one of the difficulties. Unlike the non-periodic variables used in many methods such as SBM, circular variables have two alternative paths (clockwise and counterclockwise) to move around the circle. With gradient descent, a variable moves by an amount that is the sum over all of its interactions. If the contributions are in opposite

directions, the sum can approach zero and the variable can remain stationary, even if a lower energy configuration were possible by rotating 180 degrees. The scenario is analogous to a coordination failure in multi-agent systems, when agents agree on a goal but do not achieve a consensus on which of two directions to pursue. This is a particular type of sub-optimal, meta-stable state we refer to as a *circular conflict trap*. A minimal example in Fig. 2 illustrates how, given (6) and (7), even a very small system can get trapped. While this example is illustrative, similar cancellation effects can arise in larger sparse graphs due to competing local interactions. Cosm institutes two key mechanisms designed to improve the search dynamics in sparse Ising-type landscapes involving circular variables.

Fig. 2. Example of a Circular Conflict Trap. (top) Seemingly trivial 3-variable Ising problem with no frustration and two ground states (up-down-down and down-up-up, Ising energy -3). (bottom) Variable trajectory using gradient descent. The variable interval wraps around from 0 to 360 degrees in a circle as with phase variables. From the particular random initial state shown, forces cancel out and the gradient is 0, leading to frozen dynamics and a suboptimal solution (Ising energy -1) no matter where the final circular space is divided into two equal halves to binarize the system. While this is a minimal example, one can envision analogous traps in much larger systems.

B. Cosm Pseudocode

The Cosm algorithm is described in pseudocode in Alg. 1. It consists of an edge coloring step, a main loop of sweeps, and a step at the end that converts the continuous variables to two-valued (i.e., binarization). With 2D and 3D lattice graph instances, an edge coloring can be trivially assigned using a regular pattern. With non-lattice graph instances, a variety of polynomial-time heuristics are possible for assigning a unique edge coloring to each instance. In this work, we employ a simple greedy heuristic that loops over the edges and assigns the lowest color number available. Within each sweep are two key features (sequential conflict-free search and dual window twist perturbations) that are covered in Sections II-C and II-D. Cosm employs a time-dependent continuous step size α_t so the

Algorithm 1 Cosm

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1: Assign a proper edge coloring of the input graph
2: Set  $\alpha_0$ 
3: Set  $x_i$  random
4: for  $sweep = 1$  to  $numSweeps$  do
5:   for each colored set of independent edges do
6:     for each edge in colored set do
7:       Update  $x_i, x_j$  according to Eq. 6
8:     end for
9:   end for
10:  if  $sweep$  is a multiple of  $DWTperiod$  then
11:    Select random reference angle  $\theta_{ref}$ 
12:    Define dual opposing windows centered at  $\theta_{ref}$ 
13:    for all  $x_i$  within windows do
14:      Rotate  $x_i$  by  $DWTRatio \times \alpha_t$ 
15:    end for
16:  end if
17:  Update  $\alpha_t$  according to step size schedule
18: end for
19: for  $p = 1$  to  $numBisectors$  do
20:   Select a candidate line bisecting the unit circle
21:   Convert  $x_i$  to two-valued  $s_i$  using the two semi-circles
22:   Evaluate the original binary objective function
23: end for
24: Return best solution

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system can be annealed [12]; an example annealing schedule is a linear ramp from α_0 down to 0. After annealing, the unit circle is bisected into two halves, and variables in one half are assigned -1 and in the other $+1$. Problems that have local bias fields have defined semicircular sections and thus this binarization step is trivial. For problems that do not have local bias fields, a procedure is needed to find an effective bisector. Here, we employ a set of equally-spaced bisectors and select the best resulting solution (an alternative algorithm, which finds the optimal bisector, is provided in Ref. [27]).

C. Sequential Conflict-free Search (SCS)

To improve the efficacy of the search process, Cosm assigns the input graph G a proper edge coloring with C colors (Fig. 3a), such that the edge set E_G is partitioned as

$$E_G = E_1 \cup E_2 \cup \dots \cup E_C, \quad (9)$$

where each subset E_c corresponds to a matching (i.e., no two edges share a common vertex) associated with color c . A minimum coloring of the graph is not required.

The objective function (7) is correspondingly decomposed as

$$f(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{c=1}^C f_c(\mathbf{x}), \quad (10)$$

where

$$f_c(\mathbf{x}) = - \sum_{(i,j) \in E_c} J_{ij} v(x_i, x_j). \quad (11)$$

Rather than updating the system using the full gradient of $f(\mathbf{x})$, the Cosm update rule cyclically applies gradients of the individual components f_c . Specifically, at iteration t , the update is given by

$$\mathbf{x}_{t+1} = \mathbf{x}_t - \alpha_t \nabla f_{c(t)}(\mathbf{x}_t), \quad (12)$$

Fig. 3. Edge-Coloring for Sequential Conflict-Free Search. a) Cosm first assigns a proper edge coloring of the input graph, either by loading a standard coloring or generating one using a polynomial-time heuristic. b) The edge colored graph is separated by color into C matchings (graphs for which degree ≤ 1), ensuring there are no conflicting interactions. The system evolves according to the pairwise interactions of one color at a time and repeats in a sequence, representing a dynamical system on a conflict-free periodically switched network.

Fig. 4. Example of Cosm's Sequential Conflict-Free Search (SCS) Dynamics. (upper left) Three-variable problem instance after edge coloring. (bottom) System evolution in a periodic sequence of red, green, and blue interactions. Line segments are illustrated with the color of the associated interaction; when a variable is not involved in an interaction, it maintains its state (black dotted lines). Unlike the frozen dynamics shown in Fig.2, the system escapes from the circular conflict trap and very quickly (1 sweep) reaches a configuration corresponding to the optimal solution (Ising energy -3).

where the active partition index is defined as

$$c(t) = ((t - 1) \bmod C) + 1 \quad (13)$$

and $\nabla f_{c(t)}$ is a selected generalized gradient using (5). Thus, the algorithm performs a deterministic rotation over the C edge partitions. Effectively, the system evolves on a network for which the edge set changes in time. This is a particular type of switched (time-varying) network we refer to as a *periodically switched network*. At each point in time a variable is connected to at most one other variable and thus each edge set is free of potentially conflicting interactions. The concept is illustrated in Fig. 3b. We refer to the dynamical systems

strategy utilizing such a network as *sequential conflict-free search* (SCS).

In SCS, the processing of all edges of a given color is referred to as a sub-sweep, and processing all edges in the problem graph is a *sweep* consisting of C sub-sweeps. SCS leads to *intra-sweep variable fluctuations* in which variable movements (phase rotations) accumulate from sub-sweep to sub-sweep. These lead to unique dynamics that can empirically improve performance. A minimal example of SCS dynamics and fluctuations is shown in Fig. 4. Unlike the baseline gradient descent example shown in Fig. 2, the system avoids a circular conflict trap and quickly reaches an optimal configuration. A visualization of Cosm dynamical system evolution, including the use of SCS and resulting intra-sweep fluctuations, is provided in Fig. 6.

D. Dual Window Twist (DWT) Perturbations

Complementing the deterministic SCS rules, Cosm institutes a novel type of perturbation of the spin variables. The intent is to perturb the system such that sets of variables that have emerged with members at opposite regions of phase space, which we refer to as *polarized clusters*, can be perturbed together and made more likely to separate and rotate freely to lower energy configurations. At occasional times during system evolution, Cosm selects two diametrically opposed equal-sized windows centered around a random reference angle θ_{ref} along the unit circle. All variables found to be within either of

Fig. 5. Visualization of Cosm Dynamics with a Dual Window Twist (DWT) Perturbation. Variables are shown as filled-in circles residing on a unit circle. a) The system is initialized to a uniform random state. b) In addition to variable movements due to Sequential Conflict-free Search, at regular intervals a pair of dual opposing windows (shaded) is defined at a random angle. Variables within the windows are selected for perturbation. c) Variables within the dual windows are rotated by an amount proportional to the current step size α_t , after which the dynamics continue. d) Example system configuration after an annealing cycle (solver run) with multiple sweeps and DWT perturbations.

Fig. 6. Example Cosm Dynamical System Evolution. a) Variables wrap around in the circular phase space. b) Example dynamics resulting from sequential conflict-free search (SCS) and sgn-based pairwise interactions, including intra-sweep fluctuations. The encircled trajectory spans three sweeps with four sub-sweeps (edge-colored interactions) per sweep. c) DWT perturbations are visible as discontinuities after every 10th sweep, affecting variables within randomly placed dual 90-degree windows separated by 180 degrees. d) Example of a polarized cluster move beginning near sweep 30 when three variables (one in the upper half of phase space and two in the lower) decrease their angular position together through sweep 60; the three variables (3, 6, and 7 using 1-based numbering) represent a contiguous, coupled chain in the problem graph. The Ising problem comes from Ref. [11] (2D toroidal spin glass, $L=4$, 16 variables, instance no. 31, $J_{ij} \in \{\pm 1, \pm 2\}$). The first 60 sweeps of a 300-sweep anneal are shown.

the two windows rotate their positions together by the same magnitude and in the same direction. We refer to this as a *dual window twist* (DWT) perturbation. No information is needed about the existence or location of polarized clusters. DWT is a type of correlated perturbation that incorporates a stochastic aspect due to the random reference angle. The DWT perturbation concept is illustrated in Fig. 5 and pseudocode provided in Alg. 1. Fig. 6 shows an example of Cosm dynamical system evolution that includes DWT perturbations and cluster motion.

By rotating dual opposing windows rather than a single window, the achieved alignment and anti-alignment relationships among variables within the windows are approximately maintained (Fig. 5b,c). The width of the windows is a tunable parameter; we find empirically that a width of 90 degrees (leading to exactly half of the phase space being included in the twist) is effective on the problems tested. The direction of the twist (clockwise or counter-clockwise) can be randomized, though with 90-degree windows and without local bias fields, we find that use of a single direction is sufficient due to symmetry. The magnitude of rotation is changed over time according to a schedule; in this work, we set the magnitude to a constant factor (e.g., 1.0) of the current step size α_t .

In concert with Cosm’s other features, the DWT mechanism is meant to promote energy-improving many-variable moves. Achieving useful cluster moves has long been an aim in binary optimization. Among spin glass simulation methods, there are replica cluster moves such as Houdayer [28] and isoenergetic cluster moves [7]. These require simulating multiple replicas of a system, comparing binary states, and flipping the binary states of selected clusters. Such moves randomize the configurations and can in some cases greatly accelerate simulations.

Cosm, assisted by DWT, is an alternative approach in which clusters of variables in a continuous circular space emerge, separate, and move in a single dynamical system.

E. Cosm Implementation

Cosm possesses several properties that make it amenable to efficient implementation. First, no double-precision arithmetic is needed, enabling reduced computational and hardware overhead. Second, it primarily employs deterministic rules and mechanisms and consumes a low rate of pseudorandom bits. Aside from random initialization of the variable vector, only a single global random value is applied once every few sweeps during system evolution, to define the location of the DWT perturbation. This contrasts with methods that require random bits for each variable and update. Third, by construction, Cosm operates on sets of edge-disjoint interactions, allowing all edges within a given color class to be processed in parallel. This structure supports potential parallel implementations on platforms such as GPUs, wafer-scale engines [29], FPGAs, and custom ASICs.

In this work, we implement Cosm in C and evaluate its performance on a CPU, as described in Section III.

III. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

We test Cosm on three types of sparse benchmark problems: large Gset 2D lattice graph spin glasses, large Gset non-lattice graph problems with bounded degree, and a set of synthetic 2D lattice graph instances with tuned hardness. We implement Cosm in C and run it on a server CPU (Intel Xeon Gold 6544Y). We refer to this solver setup as Cosm-CPU. Implementation details are given in Appendices B and C.

A. Performance on the Largest Gset 2D Spin Glasses

For binary quadratic optimization, the Gset suite [30] constitutes a canonical benchmark collection of Max-Cut and Ising-type problems. Originally developed between 1999 [31] and 2000 [6], it has since been widely adopted to assess the performance of both conventional solvers and physics-inspired Ising machine models.

First, we select the three largest instances in the Gset suite. These instances—G72, G77, and G81—are equivalent to 2D spin glasses with degree-4 nearest neighbor connectivity, bimodal ($\pm J$) couplings, and a toroidal graph structure (periodic boundary conditions in both dimensions). Searching for the ground state of an Ising spin glass defined on a lattice graph (Edwards-Anderson spin glass) is a canonical problem in condensed matter physics [20] as well as an established benchmark for binary quadratic optimization [18]. While many nonplanar Ising problems are NP-hard, the toroidal square grid problem with $\pm J$ couplings and no local bias fields is an exceptional case [32] and admits a fast heuristic method [33]. However, these three instances with 10,000–20,000 variables have not been easily solved. Before Cosm, the best reported cuts were 7006, 9938, and 14056.

For each instance, we find that Cosm finds a better solution than reported by any other method. The new best known cuts are 7008, 9940, and 14060. Cosm solution bitstrings for all three problems are posted in Refs. [34] [35] to allow the solutions to be independently validated.

Here we also supply the three instances to an exact solver, Gurobi 12.0.3. The Gurobi runs certify that the 7008, 9940, and 14060 solutions are in fact the *optimal* solutions for these 25-year old problems. Ref. [36] similarly found that a recent version of Gurobi could prove optimality for these instances (though the solutions were not provided). Cosm finds that the associated Ising ground state energies are -14022 , -19672 , and -28086 . Table I summarizes the problem instance properties and Cosm solutions.

TABLE I
COSM FINDS THE CERTIFIED OPTIMAL SOLUTIONS TO THE LARGEST GSET INSTANCES. N : NUMBER OF VARIABLES, E_G : SET OF EDGES.

Gset Instance	N	$ E_G $	Max degree	Best previous solution	Cosm solution	Cosm solution quality
G72	10000	20000	4	7006 [37]	7008	Certified optimal
G77	14000	28000	4	9938 [37]	9940	Certified optimal
G81	20000	40000	4	14056 [38]	14060	Certified optimal

TABLE II
COSM SWEEPS-TO-SOLUTION

Gset Instance	Sweeps per Trial ($\times 10^6$)	Cosm Solution	P_s	R_{99}	Sweeps-to-Solution ($\times 10^6$)
G72	1.0	7008	$405/1024 = 0.3955$	9.15	9.2
G77	1.0	9940	$237/1024 = 0.2314$	17.49	17.5
G81	2.0	14060	$20/1024 = 0.0195$	233.47	467.0

One measure of heuristic performance is sweeps-to-solution (STS), which is the number of sweeps required to ensure

reaching the optimal solution with 99% confidence (Appendix A). The Cosm STS values are shown in Table II. There are not yet any comparable STS results in the literature for these instances. As one point of comparison, a recent study tested eight different quantum-inspired and physics-inspired heuristics on instance G81. After 1000 trials of 10^5 steps/trial, the highest cuts attained were roughly 13800 to 14000 [14]. Direct comparison is difficult due to potentially different notions of steps and sweeps. However, we note that in 1000 trials of 10^5 sweeps, Cosm attains a G81 cut of 14056. Additional data on Cosm’s highest and average G81 solutions for different run lengths are provided in Ref. [35].

The wall clock times-to-solution using the Cosm-CPU setup depend on the assumed level of parallelism. Assuming use of all 32 CPU cores and two threads per core, the average execution times per trial for G72, G77, and G81 are 1.41, 1.98, and 5.68 s, respectively, giving wall clock time-to-solution (TTS) values of 12.9, 34.7, and 1326.1 s.

To gain empirical insight into Cosm dynamics, we previously examined several successful G72 trajectories [39] in detail. By assigning binary values at intermediate points (normally only performed at the end of an anneal) and testing which of the many variable transitions were consequential, we identified the critical state transition in each trajectory allowing Cosm to exceed a cut of 7006 and reach the new best (optimal) solution of 7008. We found that, in some trials, near-simultaneous flips of multiple variable clusters in separate regions of the toroidal graph were responsible. In four trials, a flip of a single contiguous cluster was responsible; the sizes of those clusters were 29, 35, 122, and 204 variables. These observations provide empirical evidence of non-local collective transitions during the search process. Note that a cluster of 204 variables represents more than 2% of the entire system. The layout of the observed 204-variable cluster on the problem lattice is illustrated in Fig. 7. The cluster has 128 pairwise bonds at its interface (i.e., with variables outside of the cluster). When the 204 continuous variables flipped, the number of satisfied bonds at the interface increased from 63

Fig. 7. Spatial Layout of a Large Cluster of Variables (shaded) Representing the Final Move Enabling the New Best and Optimal Solution to Gset Instance G72 (7008). Adapted from Ref. [39]. The cluster is visualized on a 24x25 subset of the 100x100 toroidal problem graph. Each square cell represents a variable. The cluster size is 204 variables, representing over 2% of all problem variables. The cluster has 128 pairwise bonds at its interface (connections to non-shaded cells). Variables in the cluster each changed their continuous state to reach the opposite binary state, increasing the number of satisfied bonds at the interface from 63 to 65 and improving the cut from 7006 to 7008.

to 65, improving the cut from 7006 to 7008.

B. Performance on the Largest Gset Bounded-Degree Non-Lattice Graph Instances (G61, G70)

We test Cosm on the two largest Gset bounded-degree non-lattice graph instances, G61 and G70. Bounded degree refers to problems for which the coupling degree does not grow with the size of the problem, for instance due to physical constraints (e.g., in road networks or VLSI digital circuits). The two problem graphs have irregular structure and maximum node degrees of 14 and 9, respectively. Key properties of these instances are summarized in Table III.

TABLE III
PROBLEM CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LARGEST BOUNDED-DEGREE NON-LATTICE GRAPH GSET INSTANCES. N : NUMBER OF VARIABLES, E_G : SET OF EDGES.

Gset Instance	N	$ E_G $	Max Degree	Avg Degree	Weights
G61	7000	17148	14	4.9	$\{-1, +1\}$
G70	10000	9999	9	2.0	Unweighted

This problem type is NP-hard and empirically difficult for heuristic optimizers to reach even near-best known solution quality. Recent efforts have reported incremental improvements on these benchmarks under highly specialized conditions. An evolutionary algorithm called the Large Population Island (LPI) framework by Goudet et al. reached a new best known solution of 5799 for G61 during extensive calibration runs using an NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU [40]. Subsequent evaluation runs reached a high of 5798. Similarly, a Monte Carlo gradient-based heuristic by Chen et al. reached a new best known solution of 9595 for G70 (first reported in 2023 [41]) after prolonged execution using an NVIDIA Tesla A100 GPU. During standard testing, it reached a maximum cut of 9572 [42].

We find that Cosm reaches the best known solutions for each of the instances—5799 for G61 and 9595 for G70—with regularity. A comparison of Cosm solution quality with other notable results is given in Table IV.

TABLE IV
HIGHEST CUTS ATTAINED

Solver Approach	G61	G70
Cosm (this work)	5799	9595
Large population island - calibration [40]	5799	9595
Large population island - test [40]	5798	9594
Fixstars Amplify Annealing Engine [43][44]	5796	9582
Simulated bifurcation machine [8]	5796	9578
Simulated annealing [13]	5788	9546
Breakout Local Search [45]	5789	9541
Monte Carlo policy gradient - calibration [42]	n/a	9595
Monte Carlo policy gradient - test [42]	5748	9572
D-Wave Hybrid [13]	5750	9516
CirCut [27]	5690	9529
Physics-inspired graph neural network [1]	n/a	9421

To the best of our knowledge, no prior work has reported success probabilities for reaching the current best known solutions on these instances. In contrast, the performance of Cosm

is sufficiently consistent to permit such a characterization. Over 256 independent trials of 1.28×10^8 sweeps, Cosm reaches the best known solution in 25.4% of G61 trials and 75.8% of G70 trials (Table V).

TABLE V
COSM SUCCESS PROBABILITY, 128M SWEEPS

Gset Instance	Successes/Trials	P_s
G61	65/256	0.254
G70	194/256	0.758

We measure the speed of the Cosm-CPU setup using the wall clock time-to-target (TTT) metric, defined as the expected time required to reach a specified solution quality with 99% probability (Appendix A). Measurements of average execution time per trial cover the annealing time including the binarization step at the end of each trial. We do not include the time for edge coloring which is performed once per instance. Edge coloring is performed off-line using the greedy heuristic from Section II-B; using MATLAB, the edge coloring takes 3.2 s (G61) and 1.7 s (G70). Although a minimum coloring is not strictly necessary, the edge coloring heuristic colors these graphs using the minimum number (14 and 9 colors). The numbers of edges assigned each color are provided in Appendix B. For each benchmark instance, we conduct 64,000 independent trials. Empirically, we observe that the solver achieves high efficiency when processing batches of $r \approx 256$ –512 trials concurrently. Accordingly, we employ short trial lengths (0.5M sweeps per trial for G61 and 0.2M for G70) and select $r \approx 512$ and $r \approx 256$, respectively, to minimize TTT.

Under this configuration, Cosm-CPU achieves a wall clock TTT of 303 s on G61 and 36 s on G70 for the best known solutions. To the best of our knowledge, TTT values for these solution qualities have not been previously reported.

To provide context for these results, we consider the best previous reported results. The only solver of which we are aware to have reached the best known solution on G61 (5799) is the Goudet et al. LPI algorithm [40], which reached this target during hundreds of hours of calibration runs on a V100 GPU. The target was not reached during 20-hour test runs. While the hardware used is not directly comparable, the Cosm-CPU TTT of 303 s on G61 is in a very different performance regime under the tested conditions. To reach a target one unit below the best known values, Goudet et al. report times of 74,373 s for G61 (cut 5798), and 28,820 s for G70 (cut 9594). Thus, the Cosm-CPU results are approximately 2–3 orders of magnitude faster (303 and 36 s) and simultaneously more accurate. The Simulated Bifurcation Machine (SBM) attained a wall clock TTT of 31,599 s to reach a cut value of 9578 on G70 using an NVIDIA Tesla V100 GPU [8]; for this solution quality, Cosm-CPU requires ~ 2 s. A summary of Cosm TTT results is provided in Table VI.

To assess the extent to which two of Cosm’s key features contribute to performance, we conduct an ablation study comparing Cosm against three alternative algorithms for which SCS is disabled, DWT is disabled, and both SCS and DWT

TABLE VI
COSM-CPU WALL CLOCK TIME-TO-TARGET (TTT) RESULTS. R_{99} :
REPETITIONS FOR 99% SUCCESS PROBABILITY.

Gset Instance	Highest Cut Achieved	P_s (64,000 trials)	R_{99}	Cosm Sweeps-to-Target ($\times 10^6$)	Cosm-CPU Wall Clock TTT (s)
G61	5799	0.008328	550.7	275	303.3
G70	9595	0.01872	243.7	48.7	35.9

are disabled, respectively. In all four cases, 1000 trials of Gset problem G70 are performed, with 1.5M sweeps/trial. The results are shown in Table VII. With this run length of 1.5M sweeps, Cosm achieves the best known solution in 16.3% of trials and an average cut of 9593.39. In the three other cases, the highest achieved cuts are well below the best known, and the average cuts are dramatically lower than Cosm. This result provides evidence that both SCS and DWT are essential to Cosm’s performance. Example energy trajectories for the four variants are provided in Fig. 8. System energy is sampled once every 1000 sweeps. Strong energy fluctuations are seen in the two algorithm variants employing DWT perturbations. The included Cosm data are from a run reaching the lowest known Ising energy (-9191 , corresponding to the best known cut of 9595).

TABLE VII
ABLATION EXPERIMENT RESULTS. 1000 TRIALS OF INSTANCE G70.
1.5M SWEEPS/TRIAL FOR EACH ALGORITHM VARIATION. COSM FINDS
THE BEST KNOWN SOLUTION ON 16% OF TRIALS. PERFORMANCE DROPS
PRECIPITOUSLY WHEN DISABLING SEQUENTIAL CONFLICT-FREE SEARCH
(SCS) OR DUAL WINDOW TWIST (DWT) PERTURBATIONS.

Algorithm	Highest Cut	Avg Cut	P_s
Cosm	9595	9593.39	0.163
without SCS	9551	9528.00	0
without DWT	9544	9501.40	0
no SCS, no DWT	9481	9432.81	0

Fig. 8. Example Energy Evolution for Cosm and Three Alternatives Tested on Instance G70 in Ablation Study. In this run, Cosm reached the lowest known Ising energy (-9191), corresponding to the best known cut (9595).

C. 2D Tile-Planted Instances

To test Cosm on an additional sparse problem type outside of the Gset suite, we consider a set of 2D lattice instances that were crafted in Ref. [11] using the Chook benchmark instance generator [46]. The weights come from the set $\{\pm 1, \pm 2\}$; the use of two weight magnitudes allows tuning of the problem hardness [47]. The problem graphs have degree-4 nearest neighbor connectivity and periodic boundaries in both dimensions. By construction, using the tile-based approach, each instance has a known ground state making the set suitable for benchmarking. The collection consists of 100 instances for each problem size ranging from 16 to 1024 variables, where the number of variables $N = L^2$ and $L \in \{4, 6, 8, \dots, 32\}$.

These instances were used in an extensive comparative study of stochastic driven non-linear dynamical systems by Hou et al. [11]. Seven prominent solver algorithms were tested including simulated annealing, simulated coherent Ising machine (SimCIM), OIM, and a version of SBM. Since many of the solvers were unable to attain ground states for the larger problem sizes, scaling characterization was limited to the five largest sizes shown in Fig. 1 of Ref. [11], corresponding to sizes of $L \in \{12, 14, 16, 18, 20\}$. The authors found that the median TTS data for simulated annealing and SimCIM fit to the lowest (best) scaling exponents, in the range of 0.22 to 0.25.

We obtained the Chook-generated instances from the authors and tested Cosm (details in Appendix C). We first find that, unlike many of the solvers in [11], Cosm attains the ground state of all instances and all sizes in the set within the tested sweep budgets, including the largest instances with $N = 1024$. Specifically, at $N = 1024$ with 10,000 trials and 1000 sweeps/trial, the Cosm median P_s across the 100 instances is $P_s = 2.09\%$ and the median STS is 2.18×10^5 sweeps.

Though absolute runtimes are not directly comparable due to different codebases and hardware, scaling exponent comparisons are more robust to implementation differences. Thus, we estimate the scaling of median TTS vs. L for

Fig. 9. Comparison of TTS Scaling Exponents of Eight Solvers on Tile-Planted Benchmark Instances. Error bars are shown for seven other solvers; data were extracted from Ref. [48] and re-plotted and should be considered approximate. Cosm’s 95% confidence interval is shown on the right.

Cosm over the same problem sizes as Ref. [11], namely $L \in \{12, 14, 16, 18, 20\}$ (144 to 400 variables). As with Ref. [11], we use a single CPU core when measuring execution time. From measured P_s values and average execution times over 10,000 trials for each of median instances, we calculate median TTS at each problem size and fit the data using the same method as Ref. [11] (linear fit to $a+bL$ in the logarithmic scale). We obtain an estimated value for the slope (scaling exponent b) of 0.139 (95% confidence interval: 0.104–0.175). This value is lower than the scaling exponents reported for the seven previously characterized solvers, including simulated annealing and SimCIM (0.22–0.25). The data are plotted in Fig. 9. Additionally, we characterize Cosm scaling over a wider range of sizes ($L \in \{12, 14, \dots, 32\}$), and obtain a scaling exponent of 0.128.

IV. RELATED WORK

Related work has been conducted in dynamical systems for combinatorial optimization [11]; Cosm is distinct in that it relies predominantly on deterministic switched dynamics and non-smooth interactions to sustain persistent fluctuations during the search process. SBM is a deterministic approach in which virtual particles move according to quantum-inspired equations of motion [8]. The discrete variant in particular, called dSB, uses sgn-based coupling as Cosm does, though unlike Cosm the phase space is non-periodic and there is no notion of switched dynamics or DWT. A recent OIM approach pursues sgn-based coupling [26] within a periodic phase space, though again without switched dynamics or DWT.

Stochastic gradient descent—used widely for training deep neural networks—has a conceptual connection to Cosm’s SCS; in both cases search is performed not using the gradient of the loss (objective) function but rather a sequence of gradients of small portions of the function. However, Cosm updates are predominantly deterministic and cyclic, rather than stochastic, which preserves structure in the dynamics while still breaking the symmetry of simultaneous updates. SCS is related to block-coordinate descent methods in that updates are performed on subsets of the objective function. However, Cosm is a flexible approach; for lattice graphs, all variables are updated in each sub-sweep, making it a matching-based full-space method. For non-lattice graphs, different subsets of variables are updated in each subsweep. Some existing work in binary optimization relies on *vertex* coloring for variable updates (block coordinate descent), such as a Monte Carlo probabilistic bit approach [49]; we have found scarce work in binary optimization that exploits edge coloring.

Monte Carlo methods are primarily stochastic while Cosm can be thought of as primarily structured deterministic. A reinforcement learning approach has been proposed for ground state search in lattice spin glasses [50]; its applicability to non-lattice graph problems is not clear.

Analogous to Cosm’s use of global cues to facilitate bottom-up collective behavior, recent work in cyber-physical systems, swarm robotics, and other disciplines strives for guided self-organization [51]. Note, however, that Cosm operates in open-loop fashion and does not require sensing and feedback to a

global controller. Graph cellular automata and graph neural networks have some connections with Cosm given their simple rules, support for arbitrary graphs, and collective behavior. Related to Cosm’s SCS are works on dynamic neighborhoods in cellular automata [52] and the use of time-varying networks to enhance the ability of agents to synchronize [53] [54].

V. DISCUSSION

In this section, we offer qualitative insights summarizing Cosm’s dynamical operation and discuss some limitations of the approach.

A. Theoretical Intuition and Dynamical Perspective

While Cosm is introduced as a heuristic algorithm, its behavior admits qualitative interpretation through several dynamical systems perspectives, as follows.

1) Circular Variables. The use of circular variables may itself facilitate collective motion in a way that is difficult to realize in purely binary formulations. Variables in Cosm evolve continuously on a periodic manifold, which may support coordinated rotational motion (Fig. 6d). In contrast, binary formulations generally require discrete multi-variable flips to realize analogous transitions. While circular and phase-based variables have been widely studied in oscillator Ising machines, XY systems, and synchronization dynamics, prior work has largely emphasized synchronization and continuous relaxation behavior. Here, we highlight a different potential role of periodic phase-space structure: facilitating coordinated transport of polarized variable clusters prior to binary partitioning.

2) Sgn-based interactions. The use of sgn-based interactions may contribute to maintaining active dynamics throughout the search process. Unlike smooth sinusoidal couplings, whose interaction strengths diminish continuously near equilibrium configurations, the pairwise interactions in Cosm maintain finite update magnitudes independent of angular separation (Fig. 6b). Combined with the periodically switched interaction structure, this can sustain persistent fluctuations and inhibit premature freezing into metastable states.

3) Switched, Edge-Partitioned Dynamics. Cosm replaces a simultaneous update over all edges with a cyclic sequence of updates over edge-disjoint matchings. This induces a periodically switched dynamical system, where the active interaction set changes deterministically over time, shaping the system trajectory. The network is neither static nor chaotic—it is rhythmically reconfigured. One consequence of this construction is that the resulting dynamics are non-commutative: the final state after one sweep depends on the order in which the partitions are applied. This differs fundamentally from standard gradient descent, where all interactions are aggregated into a single update. With circular variables, where competing interactions can induce cancellation, this temporal decomposition allows individual couplings to act without interference during their respective sub-sweeps. As a result, SCS can mitigate the type of force cancellation described in Section II-A by ensuring that each interaction contributes a finite update over time rather than being averaged

out instantaneously. From this perspective, SCS introduces structured deterministic fluctuations induced by periodically switched interaction topology. The system no longer follows a smooth descent trajectory, but instead traverses a sequence of piecewise flows, which can enable transitions across energy barriers that would otherwise trap the basic gradient-based method.

4) Correlated Perturbations and Cluster Motion. The DWT mechanism introduces correlated perturbations that act on extended subsets of variables at a random reference angle in phase space. Unlike independent noise or random bit flips, DWT applies a coherent rotation to variables within two opposing angular windows. Because these windows are diametrically opposed, alignment and anti-alignment relationships among coupled variables within the pair of windows are approximately preserved during the perturbation (Fig. 6c). This structure enables DWT to promote cluster-level motion and energy-improving non-local transitions that would otherwise require coordinated multi-variable flips in a binary formulation. While DWT is empirically effective on the tested benchmarks, a formal characterization of its dynamics and parameter regimes—including perturbation magnitude, frequency, and window size—remains an important direction for future work.

5) Combined Effect: Taken together, the circular representation, finite-magnitude sgn interactions, SCS, and DWT induce a form of structured non-equilibrium dynamics. SCS provides a deterministic time-varying interaction structure, while DWT injects intermittent correlated perturbations that promote large-scale rearrangements. As the annealing schedule reduces the step size α_t , intra-sweep fluctuations diminish and variable clusters contract in phase space, increasing the separation between clusters and, in some cases, eliminating overlap. Consequently, solution improvements can continue to occur near the end of an anneal as cluster structure sharpens and previously ambiguous partition boundaries become increasingly resolvable. Empirically, as illustrated in Fig. 7, Cosm dynamics can produce non-local transitions involving contiguous clusters of variables, suggesting a mechanism for escaping metastable configurations in large sparse systems. The observed cluster-level transitions may be relevant to ongoing efforts to understand the role of coordinated many-variable moves in traversing rugged energy landscapes, including in both classical and quantum optimization settings.

B. Limitations

The preceding intuition is most applicable in regimes where the problem graph is sparse and of bounded degree, such that the magnitude of intra-sweep fluctuations also remains bounded. In Cosm, the overall trajectory over a sweep is the result of a sequence of sub-sweep updates. In bounded-degree graphs, each variable participates in a limited number of interactions per sweep, and the resulting intra-sweep fluctuations—i.e., the cumulative angular displacement induced by successive sub-sweeps—remain moderate.

In contrast, in higher-degree or dense graphs, a variable may be involved in many interactions within a single sweep. This can lead to large intra-sweep fluctuations, where the net

angular displacement becomes substantial (e.g., approaching or exceeding 180 degrees). Such large rotations can cause a variable to move across energetically meaningful boundaries in the circular representation, potentially placing it on the “wrong” side of the unit circle relative to its optimal binary assignment. Thus, Cosm’s performance degradation in dense graphs is not merely due to the overhead of a large number of interaction sets.

From this perspective, the effectiveness of Cosm relies in part on a balance between structured exploration and controlled update magnitude. With its bang-bang-like coupling and intra-sweep fluctuations, Cosm dynamics can bear a qualitative resemblance to chaotic chattering in sliding mode control, where rapid switching dynamics can induce oscillatory behavior [55]. While Cosm operates in a different setting, the analogy highlights the potential importance of controlling update magnitudes in systems governed by switching dynamics.

Taken together, these observations suggest that the use of circular variables may impose an implicit constraint on the allowable magnitude of sequential updates. When this constraint is violated—e.g., through high-degree connectivity or insufficiently damped step sizes—the representation may fail to faithfully encode the underlying binary structure. A more formal characterization of intra-sweep fluctuation bounds, and their relationship to graph structure and algorithm parameters, warrants further theoretical investigation.

VI. CONCLUSION

We have introduced Collective Switched Motion (Cosm), a new heuristic for solving Ising-type optimization problems in specialized regimes. Cosm departs from conventional gradient-based approaches by employing periodically switched, edge-partitioned dynamics combined with structured perturbations, enabling efficient exploration of specialized energy landscapes. Although Cosm is not competitive or applicable for large dense problems, it excels at handling large-scale, bounded-degree graph structures. Cosm’s SCS feature is reminiscent of matching-based update rules employed in other contexts; a key finding is the extent of its effectiveness—when combined with features such as DWT—in a sparse Ising-type context.

Experimental results demonstrate that Cosm achieves optimal solutions to the three largest longstanding Gset instances, and on the two largest Gset bounded-degree non-lattice graph instances attains best known solutions with substantially reduced time-to-target compared to existing methods. Cosm attains these solutions with consistent success rates. Moreover, on a set of synthetic benchmarks, Cosm outperforms a wide range of dynamical systems heuristics. While direct runtime comparisons across different hardware platforms and experimental protocols should be interpreted with caution, the results indicate that Cosm operates in a substantially different empirical performance regime under the tested benchmark conditions. Even under conservative assumptions, the observed improvements in TTS and TTT are large relative to prior methods.

The structure of Cosm is well suited for parallel implementation, as updates operate on edge-disjoint subsets that can

be processed concurrently. This suggests a pathway toward further acceleration on massively parallel hardware platforms, including GPUs, wafer-scale systems, and custom ASICs.

Future directions include benchmarking [1] [2] [12] [15], linking Cosm to meta-heuristic frameworks, and seeking connections to neural network training for models with binary weights [56] or natively circular weights [57]. The Cosm findings may be useful for gaining insight into the structure of sparse energy landscapes [58] and how to efficiently traverse them. While the present work focuses on sparse pairwise interactions, the underlying framework naturally extends to more general settings. In particular, the partitioned update mechanism can be generalized to handle higher-degree nodes through adaptive scheduling of interaction subsets, and extended to k -local objective functions by operating on collections of hyperedges. These directions provide a pathway toward applying Cosm to a broader class of combinatorial optimization problems.

More broadly, Cosm illustrates how the interplay of simple locally interacting elements, structured switching dynamics, and global coordination can give rise to effective collective computation.

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APPENDIX A BACKGROUND

The problems of interest include sparse Ising, Max-Cut, and quadratic unconstrained binary optimization (QUBO) formulations. The Ising Hamiltonian is given in Eq. 1 in the main text. In this particular work, the problem instances do not contain local bias fields. Ising problems can alternatively be formulated as weighted Max-Cut problems

$$\max \frac{1}{2} \sum_{1 \leq i < j \leq n} w_{ij}(1 - x_i x_j) \quad (14)$$

with n binary variables $x_i \in \{-1, +1\}$ [27]. When converting between Ising and Max-Cut formulations, $w_{ij} = -J_{ij}$. Note that the Gset problem files use the Max-Cut sign convention for the weights.

Given the success probability $P_s < 1$ of reaching a solution, the number of repetitions R_{99} required to reach the solution with at least 99% probability is

$$R_{99} = \frac{\log(1 - 0.99)}{\log(1 - P_s)}. \quad (15)$$

If $P_s = 1$, r is taken to be 1 trial. As an intrinsic measure of algorithmic performance, we use sweeps-to-target which is defined as

$$STT(target) = S_{trial} \cdot R_{99} \quad (16)$$

where S_{trial} is the number of sweeps per trial. Sweeps-to-solution (STS) has the same form as STT; we use the term STS when the target is the optimal solution. To characterize our specific Cosm-CPU implementation, we employ wall clock time-to-target defined as

$$\text{Wall clock TTT}(target) = t_{trial} \cdot R_{99} \quad (17)$$

where t_{trial} is the average execution time per trial over a batch of parallel trials. Wall clock time-to-solution (TTS) has the same form as TTT; we use the term TTS when the target is the optimal solution.

APPENDIX B

EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS – GSET EXPERIMENTS

Cosm was implemented in C and compiled with GNU gcc 8.5.0 (-O3 -ffast-math option). All floating-point variables in Gset experiments used single precision. The processor employed was an Intel Xeon Gold 6544Y CPU with 32 physical cores (16 cores \times 2 sockets), 2 TB of memory, and a 3600 MHz clock frequency. Gset test campaigns generally used 64 parallel threads. Multiple replicas (independent dynamical systems, each associated with a different trial) were laid out in an interleaved fashion in memory to amortize the penalties of memory transactions; the number of parallel dynamical systems processed in interleaved fashion per thread was eight for G61 and four for all other instances. Given 64 threads, 512 trials were in flight at a time for G61 and 256 trials for all other instances.

All 2D lattice instances used a 4-color edge coloring with the same regular pattern. For non-lattice graph instances, a greedy edge coloring heuristic was used; the number of edges in each edge color partition is shown in Table VIII. Alternative heuristics are possible that use additional colors or balance the number of edges per color.

TABLE VIII
NUMBER OF EDGES PER COLOR USING GREEDY EDGE-COLORING
HEURISTIC

Gset Instance	Number of Edges per Color ($ E_1 , E_2 , \dots, E_C $)
G61	3036, 2862, 2608, 2331, 1949, 1561, 1150, 777, 467, 251, 103, 37, 12, 4
G70	3440, 2747, 1925, 1135, 523, 170, 44, 11, 4

TABLE IX
COSM SOLVER PARAMETER SETTINGS COMMON TO ALL GSET
EXPERIMENTS

Parameter	Value
Initial step size α_0	14 degrees
Final step size	0 degrees
Size of each DWT window	90 degrees
Number of bisectors for binarization	100

The Cosm solver parameter settings are given in Tables IX, X, and XI. We employed step size schedules that started from an initial value of 14 degrees and ramped down linearly to 0. The step size was updated once per sweep and stayed constant within a sweep. Solutions were read out at the end of each

TABLE X
DUAL WINDOW TWIST (DWT) PERTURBATION PARAMETER SETTINGS

Parameter	G61	G70	G72	G77	G81
Ratio of DWT step to α	1.5	1.0	0.5	0.5	0.5
Period of DWT (sweeps)	3	6	3	3	3

TABLE XI
SWEEPS/TRIAL PARAMETER SETTINGS FOR GSET STS (STT) AND TTS (TTT) EXPERIMENTS

Parameter	G61	G70	G72	G77	G81
Sweeps/trial ($\times 10^6$)	0.5	0.2	1.0	1.0	2.0

trial. Variables were binarized by performing 100 bisections of the unit circle (spaced by 1.8 degrees, covering an entire semicircle) and taking the best solution. We selected a value of 100 as a conservative value that empirically was sufficient to ensure high performance.

APPENDIX C EXPERIMENTAL DETAILS – TILE-PLANTED PROBLEM EXPERIMENTS

Cosm was tested on the tile-planted problem instances generated by the chook tool [46] and described in Ref. [11]. The problem instances were provided by one of the authors (H.K.) of Ref. [11]. There are 100 instances at each problem size N from 16 to 1024 variables, where $N = L^2$ and $L \in \{4, 6, 8, \dots, 32\}$. The Ising ground state energy was provided for each instance.

Using a MATLAB-based implementation of Cosm, we confirmed that Cosm reaches the ground state for all instances and all problem sizes ($L \in \{4, 6, 8, \dots, 32\}$).

For characterizing scaling, the selected problem sizes ranged from 144 to 400 variables ($L \in \{12, 14, 16, 18, 20\}$) to match Ref. [11]. At each size, the number of sweeps was tuned to optimize sweeps-to-solution and an instance with median P_s was identified using MATLAB. The execution times of the five median instances were then measured using a C implementation of Cosm. (Note that while MATLAB was used for parameter tuning and identifying median instances, all reported timing results are based on a C implementation.) The hardware used was the same CPU described in Appendix B (Intel Xeon Gold 6544Y). Unlike the Gset experiments, C floating-point variables during these particular experiments defaulted to double precision. Solver parameter settings included the following: initial step size $\alpha_0 = 25$ degrees; ratio of DWT step to $\alpha = 1.0$; DWT period = 3 sweeps. Average execution times per trial were measured by performing 10,000 sequential trials of each median instance using a single job. For lattice instances, Cosm used a standard edge coloring that is trivial to assign; the time required to assign colors in pre-processing is not included in execution time measurements. Here, only a single trial was solved at a time (no interleaving of multiple trials); use of sequential trials and a single job matches Ref. [11] which used a single CPU core. The observed P_s and average execution time were used to calculate the median TTS.

The measured TTS values for sizes $L = 12, 14, 16, 18, 20$ are 6.101 ms, 14.589 ms, 28.739 ms, 53.492 ms, and 78.159 ms, respectively. To match the methodology described in [11], we fit $\log_{10}TTS$ data to $a + bL$ and obtain a slope of 0.139, representing the scaling exponent b . The coefficient of determination R^2 is 0.981 and the lower and upper 95% confidence bounds are 0.104 and 0.175.

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BIOGRAPHY SECTION

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